

Design for all life

Guest editor,
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In many design situations, animals, plants, fungi, and bacteria are better clients than humans. These nonhuman beings live diverse, interesting, and grossly under-explored lives, making research exciting and new discoveries easy.

They are in control of real riches: energy, oxygen, and nutrients, rather than abstract dollar amounts. Importantly, nonhuman lifeforms innovate. All have forms of subjectivity, all communicate and process information, many have lasting cultures. All are successful, simply because they have survived. Today, millions of lifeforms experience human-caused extinctions. In most cases, complete remediation is impossible but remarkable improvements are accessible and morally imperative.

Engagement with nonhuman clients and collaborations can be challenging. They cannot read project briefs or assess drawings. Many live cryptic lives. Few have any commitment to human projects. Some actively resist surveillance or intrusion. However, these challenges should not prevent action. On the contrary, they reveal opportunities for improvements in ethics, politics, aesthetics, cultures, and technology.

To give some examples, design projects of our Deep Design Lab at the University of Melbourne investigate practical approaches to interspecies justice. For example, we have explored designing for nonhuman capabilities,¹ built habitat structures

that take inspiration from arboreal termite nests as shown on the next page, proposed smart systems to minimise environmental light pollution,² initiated a reconsideration of smart cities in more-than-human terms,³ and developed tools for more-than-human heritage.⁴

We find that more-than-human approaches to design can be compatible with human needs, creatively liberating and ethically upstanding. Every architect needs a client, but not all clients are rewarding. A powerful prince or a rich corporation might have the capacity for large-scale construction but an aversion to go beyond conventions or little commitment to the interests of others.

How does the collaboration with nonhumans relate to the current debates about the role of design? Many see human designers as the purveyors of progress. Designers support development and enable growth. Yet products of human ingenuity including writing, cities, and agriculture have enabled the global damage exacerbated by the ecological imperialism in recent history and the extractive economies of today. Techno-optimists advise further expansion through

deep-sea mining, geoengineering, extra-terrestrial manufacturing, and settlements on Mars. Design rooted in existing systems performs at large scales, but is it successful?

Unfortunately, many impacts of design are catastrophically destructive to life. Design rationalises, streamlines, standardises, and simplifies. It also extracts, pollutes, and induces excessive consumption. Geodiversity, biodiversity, cultural complexity – the richness of life on Earth and with it its wellbeing – diminish as a direct consequence of many current design practices.

Design's negative impacts have led to shifts in thinking. In densely populated Europe, a growing impulse is to abstain from new building and to reuse instead. The commitments to energy efficiency and forms of greening are also growing. But is mitigation enough? Will it be possible to reverse the obliteration of life by tweaking the extractive systems that – after all – are working as intended? Evidence shows that improvements within business-as-usual will not suffice.

Instead, we endorse a substantial restructuring of societies in more-than-human terms. A common way to argue for the importance of nonhuman life is to highlight the usefulness of biodiversity, the interconnectedness of all ecosystems, the moral worth of nonhuman beings, or the suffering induced by human actions. These reasons are significant, and we rely on them in our projects.

In addition, we propose that designing for and with nonhuman beings is the most exciting, rewarding, intellectually challenging, and consequential approach to creative practice. At the Deep Design Lab, we investigate ethical foundations and practical methods of this approach.⁵ We understand design as preparation for future events that can involve but does not require humans. All living beings can self-design and affect others, acting as niche constructors and ecosystem engineers. Human-driven forms of design produce huge effects but remain a component within this picture. The following diagrams position this approach visually.

The aim of design is in redirection from business as usual towards a preferable destination. Our first diagram shows this by building on existing discussions of future cones.⁶ These cones do not acknowledge that preferences diverge, sometimes dramatically, between different clients. In the context of limited knowledge and vested interests, the dominant control by any one group – and humans increasingly wield excessive powers – will harm the outsiders. To counter this, we argue for

nonhuman participation in all forms of governance, including design.

Today, non-anthropocentric design is rare. Our second diagram extends the comparison of attitudes towards the environment⁷ by linking degrees of human bias to design frameworks. Here, the Unrestrained section contains worldviews that permit environmental exploitation. Attitudes within the Shallow section accept that humans have some ethical responsibilities towards nonhuman life and consider future human generations. This section remains clearly anthropocentric and includes current frameworks such as sustainable development goals, nature capital, nature-based solutions, and ecosystem services. Positions within the Intermediate section allow the exploitation of the environment and its nonhuman inhabitants for serious human needs. They also presume that humans know best and can find solutions to emerging problems. Finally, the worldviews within the Deep section accept that some issues can be more significant than even the most serious human concerns. These attitudes also acknowledge significant limitations of human knowledge and prefer to aim for just processes rather than predefined destinations. This ecocentric position deserves more attention from designers and motivates the work of our group.⁸

We are far from alone in the effort to support nonhuman life. The articles herewith attest to the growing interdisciplinary interest towards more-than-human concerns. Matthew Darmour-Paul, Sophie Canaris, and Danielle Celermajer open the conversation by discussing visual experiences of birds and linking them to forms of social engagement that can lead to flourishing. Kylie Soanes expands on this invitation by discussing many opportunities for multispecies living in urban environments, appealing to the powers of interdisciplinary collaboration and citizen participation.

Furthering this argument, Dan Parker outlines an inclusive design approach that aims to help arboreal wildlife. His technical platform makes current evidence and technology accessible to a broad range of human stakeholders. Wolfgang W. Weisser and Thomas E. Hauck provide further context to forms of design that see nonhuman lifeforms as clients. Their framework includes the needs of urban animals as represented by human scientists and the evidence they collect.

Left page:

A prosthetic habitat-structure for the powerful owl in the System Garden, the University of Melbourne. The project and photo by Deep Design Lab.

Katherine A Dafforn, Laura Airoidi, Melanie Bishop, Tim Glasby, Alex Goad, Emma Johnston, Aria Lee, Mariana Mayer-Pinto, Emily Ravenscraft, Annie Tennant, and Maria Vozzo describe a practical example of such science-based approach to cohabitation in application to urban water edges. They frame their approach as gardening under water. Continuing with the theme of gardening as a strategic concept for cohabitation across scales, Rob Dunn's article discusses the role of microbial life and the evolutionary implications of artificial environments, with consequences for design.

Extending this theme into the realm of architecture, Richard Beckett discusses probiotic and bio-receptive approaches to architecture as a path towards better environmental and human health. Complementing approaches informed by science and engineering, Bawaka Country including Laklak Burarrwanga, Ritjilili Ganambarr, Merrkiyawuy Ganambarr-Stubbs, Banbapuy Ganambarr, Djawundil Maymuru, Kate Lloyd, Sarah Wright, Lara Daley and Sandie Suchet-Pearson emphasise the importance of close relationships with places. Such relationships call for sources of knowledge and wisdom that extend beyond science, incorporating practiced behaviours and the law of Indigenous communities.

Finally, in a stark and important reminder, Paula Arcari, Fiona Probyn-Rapsey, and Hayley Singer recast design and architecture as sources of large scale, relentless and intentional violence towards nonhuman lives and especially animals. In contrast with approaches that emphasise opportunities for cohabitation in urban spaces, this article insists on elimination of practices that normalise and institutionalise killing and suffering.

The articles herein represent a significant statement that would not be possible without the contribution of the Deep Design Lab members, the generosity of the contributing authors, and the vision of the journal's editors. In formulating the topic for this issue, the journal posed a range of open questions. What can humans learn about their own needs by designing for and through the senses of other animals? How can humans communicate with nonhuman clients? What creative opportunities emerge from encounters with clients that live in the air, in the water, or deep in the ground? What would design for all life look like? How can it be fair? The articles highlight some directions, but any substantial improvements will require a major reconsideration of design theory, education, and practice. We hope that you will join us in this effort. ■

Dr Stanislav Roudavski is an academic at the University of Melbourne, who designs for animals, plants, rivers, and rocks as well as humans. His research experiments contribute to knowledge by using scientific evidence and advanced technologies in concert with cultural, political, and historical studies.

Top right page:

Diverging preferences in design. Time flows from left to right. The darker green shows probable pasts as defined by known historical facts. The lighter green outlines the zone of conjectures informed by incomplete information. The lighter shades of grey indicate less likely futures as extrapolated from current practices. The squares suggest that preferable futures of different clients never coincide but always overlap. Diagram by Deep Design Lab.

Bottom right page:

Attitudes towards nonhuman life and design. The range is from the anthropocentric attitudes on the left to the ecocentric attitudes on the right. The white texts highlights examples of design practices. The deep green region on the right is most important but today the shallow approaches are much more common. Diagram by Deep Design Lab.

Notes

¹ Parker, Dan, Kylie Soanes, and Stanislav Roudavski. 2022. "Interspecies Cultures and Future Design." *Transpositiones* 1 (1): 183-236. <https://doi.org/10/gpvfs>; Parker, Dan, Stanislav Roudavski, Thérésa M. Jones, Nick Bradsworth, Bronwyn Isaac, Martin T. Lockett, and Kylie Soanes. 2022. "A Framework for Computer-Aided Design and Manufacturing of Habitat Structures for Cavity-Dependent Animals." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 13 (4): 826-41. <https://doi.org/10/gpggfj>.

² <https://vimeo.com/stanislavroudavski/intelligent-lighting>

³ <https://vimeo.com/stanislavroudavski/sentience>

⁴ Roudavski, Stanislav, and Julian Rutten. 2020. "Towards More-than-Human Heritage: Arboreal Habitats as a Challenge for Heritage Preservation." *Built Heritage* 4 (4): 1-17. <https://doi.org/10/ggpv66>.

⁵ <https://wiki.deepdesignlab.online>

⁶ Voros, Joseph. 2003. "A Generic Foresight Process Framework." *Foresight* 5 (3): 10-21. <https://doi.org/10/d2bj4h>.

⁷ Sylvan, Richard., 1985. *A Critique of Deep Ecology: Part 1*. Canberra: Australian National University; Andrew Vincent. 1993. "The Character of Ecology." *Environmental Politics* 2 (2): 248-76. <https://doi.org/10/dtx3m>; Hultgren, John. 2018. "21st Century American Environmental Ideologies: A Re-Evaluation." *Journal of Political Ideologies* 23 (1): 54-79. <https://doi.org/10/ggvp8h>.

⁸ Roudavski, Stanislav. 2021. "Interspecies Design." In *Cambridge Companion to Literature and the Anthropocene*, edited by John Parham, 147-62. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

